

Some Mercury(II) Complexes with Bidentate Aromatic Schiff Base Ligands

SEKHAR SRIVASTAVA* and RICHA MISHRA

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji Univeristy, Gwalior-474 011

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Since Hg^{II} complexes with Schiff base ligands are less known¹, we report here the synthesis of some Hg^{II} complexes with bidentate aromatic Schiff base ligands derived from ethylenediamine/phenylenediamine and 2-acetylpyrrole; 2-pyrrole carboxylaldehyde; 2-pyridylcarboxyaldehyde and 2-naphthylaldehyde.

Results and Discussion

Equimolar addition complexes of HgX₂ (X = Cl, NO₃) with the following Schiff base ligands have been prepared : SB₁ = bis(2-acetylpyrrole)ethylenediamine; SB₂ = bis(2-pyrrole carboxylaldehyde) ethylenediamine; SB₃ = bis(2-pyridyl carboxylaldehyde)ethylenediamine; SB₄ = bis(2-naphthylaldehyde)ethylenediamine; SB₅ = bis(2-acetylpyrrole)phenylenediamine; SB₆ = bis(2-pyrrole carboxylaldehyde)ethylenediamine; SB₇ = bis(2-naphthylaldehyde)phenylenediamine; SB₈ = bis(2-pyridylcarboxylaldehyde)phenylenediamine.

All the solid complexes are stable and insoluble in common organic solvents except DMF and DMSO. Elemental analysis ($\pm 0.5\%$ for C, H and N) and molar conductance data (less than 60 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in DMF) suggest the complexes to be non-electrolyte² with composition of HgX₂-SB. The ir bands observed at 1 610-1 660 cm^{-1} of all the ligands and the complexes are assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibration³. The ligand bands around 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N) shifted to 1 635-1 660 cm^{-1} in the complexes due to an increase of bond order on coordination⁴. The bands at 420-390 and 344-210 cm^{-1} in the complexes may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Hg-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Hg-Cl}}$ modes⁵ respectively. The nitrate complexes showed a monodentate bonding mode of nitrate in the complexes⁶.

The binding energy data of Hg4p_{1/2,3/2} photoelectron peaks for the HgX₂ and HgX₂-SB complexes showed that Hg4p_{1/2,3/2} BE value is highest in Hg(NO₃)₂ than HgCl₂. It was further noticed that Hg4p BE value in the starting material HgX₂ is higher than (having same X) in HgX₂-SB complexes (Fig. 1). These XPS data suggest that the ligands are coordinated to mercury metal ion⁷. The Hg 3s_{1/2} photoelectron peak of all the complexes have not shown multiple-splitting, suggesting diamagnetic nature of the complexes⁷.

Experimental

A mixture of the aromatic carbonyl compound (2 mmol) and the diamine (1 mmol) in methanol was refluxed for 3 h. Tlc examination suggested complete conversion of the starting materials to the Schiff base. The HgX₂ (1 mmol) was then added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. The resulting solid was washed with methanol and air-dried.

Conductance was measured in DMF at room temperature using a Digisun conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer. The X-ray photoelectron spectra were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3MK II electron spectrometer. The AlK _{α} X-ray line (1486.8 eV) was used for photoexcitation. The Cu2p_{3/2} (BE = 932.8 \pm 0.2 eV) and Au4f_{7/2} (BE = 83.8 \pm 1 eV) lines were used to calibrate the instrument and Ag3d_{5/2} (BE = 368.2 eV) was used for cross-checking⁷. All the spectra were recorded using the same spectrometer parameters of 50 eV pass-energy and 4 mm slit-width. The reduced full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) at Au4f (BE = 83.8 eV) level under these conditions was 1.2 eV. The powdered

Fig. 1. Hg $4p_{1/2}$ photoelectron peak in $HgCl_2$ and $HgCl_2$ -SB complexes.

sample was mixed with high purity silver powder to reduced charging effect. A thin layer of such sample was pressed on a gold gauze which was welded to a nickel sample holder. The $Ag3d_{5/2}$ level (BE = 368.2 eV) obtained from this sample was sharp and did not show any observable shift. Thus the charging of the sample if at all present, was negligible⁷. The spectra were recorded in triplicate in the region of interest. In most of the cases the binding energy was reproducible within ± 0.1 eV. The usual least-square fitting procedure for determining peak position, line-width and area was used.

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